

Women's Sports Development Strategy and Prospects

Annotation: *The results of the large-scale reforms carried out in our country during the years of independence, first of all, are reflected in the fact that our lives are becoming more prosperous and our achievements are being duly recognized by the world community.*

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The construction of modern sports complexes in all regions of the country, including gymnasiums, tennis courts, swimming pools, fitness halls, where female coaches work, is an important factor in the popularity of sports among girls.

Today, 48% of girls in the cities of the country and 45.7% in rural areas are involved in sports. This figure also testifies to the rapid development of women's sports in all regions of the country. Along with strengthening the health of girls, sports are expanding their worldview and raising their medical culture. The girls, trained in the classes, have a deep understanding of their responsibility to the family, society and homeland, and are married to a healthy and happy person.

Many girls have become professional athletes and are achieving great results in competitions in our country, on the continent and around the world. The fact that 38 girls were awarded the Zulfiya State Prize for their achievements in sports is an example of the attention paid to women's sports.

The State Program "Year of Healthy Mother and Child" sets out a number of measures to bring the work in this direction to a new level, to involve women in physical culture and sports, to strengthen their health.

In our region, special attention is paid to the transformation of physical culture and sports into a daily lifestyle for women through various health promotion events, competitions, tournaments, educational events.

The work carried out in this area at the Faculty of Physical Culture of Bukhara State University is also noteworthy. If we analyze the work done in the past 2012-2017, ie 5 years in the development of women's sports, we will see the following significant results:

- First, in the last 5 years, the number of female students at the Faculty of Physical Culture has increased by 20%.

- Secondly, 23 female students became winners of Uzbek, Asian and world championships in various sports.

Including: Sufidinova Yulduz (Weightlifting) 2012 Champion of Uzbekistan, 2012 Asian Champion, Bozorova Nigina (Shashka) 2010 Champion of Uzbekistan, 2nd place at the 2012 Asian Championship (Mongolia), 2012 World Championship, Islamova Nilufar (Field Hockey) 2011 Champion of Uzbekistan, 2013 International Tournament Winner (Malaysia), Sharipova Mehrangiz (Field Hockey) 2013 Champion of Uzbekistan (Tashkent), Svechnikova Darya (Rhythmic Gymnastics) 2013 Asian Champion (Tashkent), winner of international competitions.

Today, the participant of the Rio 2016 Olympics Uzbekistan and Universiade champion Nigina Sharipova, Zulfiya Award winners Sarvina Khalikova, Husniya Gulomova, talented students take part in prestigious competitions and scientific conferences and make a worthy contribution to raising the flag of our republic.

- Third, a new modern sports complex, volleyball hall, wrestling halls were built on the basis of Bukhara State University. In this complex, more than 100 girls are regularly involved in sports such as wrestling, judo, sambo, table tennis, handball, volleyball, taekwondo, gymnastics, chess, is coming.

Along with the achievements, we must admit that we have a number of problems and tasks ahead of us:

These are:

- Coordinating the activities of educational institutions, families, authorities in the development of women's sports in the community on the basis of a clear program of action.
- Introduce a sports instructor staff in the neighborhoods and plan, coordinate and organize sports competitions. To sports in the neighborhood Have an interest in identifying talented young people and directing them to the future.
- Allocation of educational quotas for sports in the faculties of physical culture.
- Involvement of the world's leading scientists and experts in the process of professional development of female teachers and coaches in the field of sports.

Theoretical knowledge and physical activity skills of women in the field of physical culture are in the focus of attention of many experts and various recommendations. However, in the process of preparing our women to participate in formal and informal public health competitions and events, they need to acquire practical knowledge and skills in the field of physical culture, ie theoretical knowledge and physical activity.

We did not observe sufficient data on the studies. Therefore, we would like to draw your attention to the following:

1. Thorough preparation for any official and unofficial health-improving public and sports competitions;
 - a) Pass a medical examination to obtain a doctor's permission to participate in the competition;
 - b) Have a clear idea of the upcoming sporting event;
 - c) Have appropriate general physical and special physical training;
 - d) Good knowledge of competition rules;
 - e) Preparation of special sportswear required for the competition;
 - f) Have a good rest for the race and prepare what you need extra;

- g) Arrive on time without late for the competition; and so on.
2. Follow the precautions when coming to the competition;
- a) Check out sportswear, numbers, essentials when leaving the residence;
- b) Clearly mark the car going to the address of the sports competition and get to the destination;
- c) Don't forget towels, soaps, etc. about the water treatment you do after the race;
3. upon arrival at the competition address:
- a) Get acquainted with the schedule of the competition, determine the time of participation;
- b) Wear sportswear required to participate in the competition;
- c) Registration at the place of gathering of participants of the competition;
- d) Gradually start performing strenuous physical activity 25-30 minutes before the start of the race or before the start of the race and bring it to the level of table speeds required for the race.
- e) 5-3 minutes before the competition, be at the highest level of preparation and listen carefully to the information about the competition by the competition organizers;

In short, thanks to independence, women's sports are growing day by day due to the wide range of opportunities created. First of all, it serves to strengthen the health of our sisters, who will create the next generation, to form a healthy lifestyle among them, and in the field of sports, our girls are high on the world sports arenas.

We are all very happy that the Uzbek women and girls are achieving their goals and demonstrating what they are capable of, raising the glory of our country.

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